

Supplementary Material

Given that MRF firing patterns are known to differ during saccades and when the animal fixates or makes slow eye movements, we excluded data from time periods during which the animals made a saccade and repeated the analyses. The approach ensured that the observed modulation of the relationship between MRF activity and pupil dynamics by visual contrast was not an artifact due to vastly different ratios of saccade to fixation MRF activity in different visual contrast conditions. We identified saccades by applying a standard velocity-threshold identification algorithm to the pupil position data. These analyses yielded similar results, which confirms that the modulation of the relationship between MRF activity and pupil dynamics by visual contrast is not an artifact due to different ratios of saccade to fixation MRF activity in different visual contrast conditions.

Supplementary Figure 1A shows the mean maximum and mean minimum values of the cross-correlation of MRF activity with vertical pupil position, horizontal pupil position, and pupil area were modulated when the visual contrast monotonically increased across both presented stimuli (left/right = 0%, left/right = 25%, left/right = 50%, and left/right = 100%). The observed trends remained the same as previously described, and we confirmed that these trends remained statistically significant by performing a one-way ANOVA across the four visual contrast levels (mean maximum cross-correlation values - vertical pupil position: $F = 132.4702$, $p < 1e-80$; horizontal pupil position: $F = 107.3209$, $p < 1e-65$; pupil area: $F = 108.9946$, $p < 1e-66$; mean minimum cross-correlation values - vertical pupil position: $F = 91.7151$, $p < 1e-56$; horizontal pupil position: $F = 137.1192$, $p < 1e-83$; pupil area: $F = 125.2628$, $p < 1e-76$). Post hoc tests with a Tukey correction confirmed that the condition where the visual contrast was 0.0 for

both the left and right presented stimulus was significantly different from any of the other three conditions for any of the examined relationships between MRN activity and pupil dynamics.

Supplementary Figure 1B shows the mean maximum and mean minimum values of the cross-correlation between MRF activity and vertical pupil position, horizontal pupil position, and pupil area across the four conditions where the visual contrast of each of the presented visual stimuli was aggregated into low (0%, and 25%) or high (50%, and 100%). The observed trends remained the same as previously described, and we confirmed that these trends remained statistically significant performing a two-way ANOVA using both the left and right visual contrast as a two-level factor. The main effect of left visual contrast, and the interaction effect of left and right visual contrast were significant for both the mean minimum and mean maximum cross-correlation values, and for any of the examined relationships between MRF activity and pupil dynamics ($F > 29$; $p < 1e-7$).

Supplementary Figure 1. Maximum and minimum cross-correlation coefficients when data from times during which the animals made saccades is excluded for the analyses. A- The mean +/- the standard error of the maximum and minimum cross-correlation coefficients of MRF activity with different pupil dynamics when gratings with the same visual contrast were presented on both sides of the screen, and **B-** when both the left and right visual stimulus had either low (0% and 25%) or high (50% and 100%) visual contrast.